



A photograph of the author during his MSc work on invasive giant hogweeds, undertaken at the University of Lausanne, Switzerland. The thesis, like many others assumes that invasive are aggressive species that will displace natives and result in the loss of biodiversity. The new wild and the concepts that emanate from it extends our static understanding of invasive species and their genes to provide alternative ways in which any species may cope with the drastic and unprecedented pace of climate change. Had the author had the clairvoyance afforded by experience, he may have come up with this theory on his own. Luckily, humanity has one large connected network of brains that operate through open access to knowledge and data and we influence each other in better our understanding of the world that surrounds us. Paradigm shifts are open for all, you may be next in line!